

NATIONAL HOLIDAYS AND TRADITIONS, THEIR CHARACTERISTICS AND IMPORTANCE

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Abstract: Holidays have become the most important and integral part of human life since ancient times. It is absolutely impossible to imagine human life without them. Holidays are a mirror that reflects the best and most beautiful aspects of people’s life. In this article, the national holidays of the Uzbek people, their unique customs and ceremonies, different views on their origin, what we celebrate and what our ancestors celebrated the stages of development of holidays are discussed.

Key words: Feast, archaeologists, ethnographers, primitive period, Zoroastrian religion, folklore, wedding, element.

Аннотация: Праздники с древнейших времен стали важнейшей и неотъемлемой частью жизни человека. Без них совершенно невозможно представить жизнь человека. Праздники – это зеркало, отражающее самые лучшие и красивые стороны жизни людей. В этой статье национальные праздники узбекского народа, их уникальные обычаи и обряды, разные взгляды на их происхождение, что празднуем мы и что праздновали наши предки на этапах развития праздников обсуждаются.

Ключевые слова: Праздник, археологи, этнографы, первобытный период, зороастрийская религия, фольклор, свадьба, стихия.

“Bayram is a day of people’s joy and happiness,” said Mahmud Koshgari, a great scientist of the East. In fact, with the help of holidays, major events, important dates, and great achievements are celebrated that create a state of joy, joy, and celebration in life. Bayram is passed by humanity itself. It helps him to deeply understand the ways he has gone, to be proud of the victories he has won, and to look at the future with good hope.

If we rely on the opinion of historians and cultural scientists that “holiday appeared and developed together with man”, the roots of the holiday can be traced back to the oldest Paleolithic period, that is, 500,000 years ago, when the human race began to appear in Central Asia. .

According to the information provided by archaeologists, historians, ethnographers, and art historians, holidays existed in the earliest times and played an important role in the life of primitive people. This opinion is also recognized by cultural scientists. For example, according to D. M. Genkin, “the deep roots of holidays go back to the “infancy” of humanity Or, as M. M. Bakhtin says, “Holidays are the initial form of human culture”

In most of the special literature, holidays are said to have originated from holiday rituals. This is generally a valid point. But many ceremonies, in turn, were created on the basis of people’s success and joy in labor and struggle, in other words, on the basis of the state of celebration. An example of this is hunting and farming rituals. On top of that, celebrations dedicated to labor are not only a ceremony, but games, competitions are organized, and even special dishes are prepared for this celebration. Thus, in the primitive period, the forms of various holidays related to work, life and religion, which were very simple like the ancient people themselves, began to emerge. These simple forms can be the basis and ground for the holidays of the following historical periods.

At the beginning of the 1st millennium BC (that is, 30-26 centuries ago), the development of sedentary farming in Central Asia, the decay of primitive society and the emergence of the slave system, the emergence of countries such as Sogd, Khorezm, Bactria in connection with the emergence of new religious views, traditions, ceremonies and holidays expressing the lifestyle characteristic of the new era also appeared.

The work of the great scientist Abu Rayhan Beruni, who lived in the 10th and 11th centuries, “Relics from Ancient Nations”, plays an important role in studying the holidays of the peoples living in the territory of Central Asia, including Uzbekistan. In his work, Beruni left invaluable historical and cultural ideas about famous days, Eids and customs in the calendar of ancient Iranians, Khorezmians, Sogdians, Romanians, Syrians, Christians, Indians and others. Most importantly for us, it provides an interesting account of the pre-Islamic annual calendar festivals of Central Asia, including the Khorezm and Sogdian peoples.

Today, Navruz is celebrated in countries such as Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Azerbaijan, Iran, Afghanistan, Turkey, which covers more than 500 million people, as well as in Russia’s Bashkortostan, Dagestan and Tatarstan. Is widely celebrated in the regions. In addition, Albania, Macedonia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Georgia, India and Pakistan, and a part of China have adopted the tradition of celebrating this day as a holiday.

There are many opinions, legends, and myths about the origin of Navroz. For example, according to some concepts of the Zoroastrian era, Ahuramaz, the god of good, ruled in spring and summer, and Ahriman, the god of evil, ruled in autumn and winter. The first day of spring was celebrated as the holy day when the god of good won over the god of evil. This date coincided with Navroz.

Alisher Navoi's work entitled "The History of Property Novice" also mentions that the great Navruz was invented after Jamshid's great discoveries. According to the legend given by Beruni, Navroz goes to King Jamshid, who has done great things: "When Jamshid made a chariot for himself, he got into the chariot that day, demons and devils lifted him into the air, and one day he left Dunbovan. Taken to Babylon they went When the people saw this wonderful event, they celebrated that day as Eid and flew on stallions in imitation of Jamshid (flying in a chariot).

It Is known from history that earlier, even if the organizers of the holiday with diplomas were not screenwriters or directors, public holidays were very interesting. Because the creator and creator of the holiday is the people themselves, the most capable and enterprising people naturally became the organizers of the holiday. Therefore, it is possible to make the holidays more enjoyable and interesting by freely developing people's initiative and creativity.

It should also be noted that if each holiday does not have its own traditions such as spectacles, games, folklore (tunes, songs, dances), they all remain the same. During the years of recession, many holidays became like that. In the process of restoration of Uzbek holidays, it is important to make each holiday its own image, appearance, and its own interest. In the multi-ethnic land of Russia, an exhibition of national art of various peoples is organized in Moscow on the occasion of Nowruz holiday. In the Volga regions, it is celebrated by playing sports and tasting national dishes. In Turkey and other countries of the Caucasus, Navrozi is also welcomed in the spirit of high morale and high morale.

In a word, Navroz not only strengthens the spirit of regional cooperation, brotherhood, good neighborliness and mutual solidarity, but also calls the countries of the world to join together in the way of a prosperous life and common interests.

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